

Search for Possible New Anthelmintic Compounds: Part IV Synthesis of 2-Substituted Benzimidazoles

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Seventeen new 2-substituted benzimidazole derivatives have been synthesized with a view to evaluate their anthelmintic activity.

A great deal of interest has recently been focussed around the synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives; because of their potential usefulness as anthelmintics¹⁻³. The broad spectrum activity of benzimidazoles is possibly due to the suppression of egg production in most of the important intestinal nematodes⁴⁻⁵.

In view of these valid observations, the authors have synthesized various 2-[(N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-piperazino carbonyl methyl)-aminoalkyl]-benzimidazoles and 2-[(β-dialkylamino-methylcarbonylamino) alkyl]-benzimidazoles incorporating > N.CO.CH₂.N < grouping in their structure. A few 2-[β-heteroaryl aryl-α-amino ethyl]benzimidazole dihydrochlorides were also prepared on similar grounds.

2-[β-heteroaryl/aryl-α-amino ethyl]-benzimidazole dihydrochlorides have been obtained by the condensation of appropriate amino acid with aromatic diamine in 5.5N-hydrochloric acid. N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-chloroacetyl piperazines were prepared by the reaction of substituted piperazines with chloroacetyl chloride in cold alkaline solution.

2-[(N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-piperazinocarbonyl methyl)-aminoalkyl]-benzimidazoles and 2-[(β-dialkylamino methyl carbonyl) amino alkyl]-benzimidazoles were prepared by condensing 2-amino alkyl benzimidazoles respectively with N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-chloroacetyl-piperazines and dialkyl amino acetyl chloride hydrochlorides in dry solvents.

Infra-red spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-137 spectrometer in KBr plates.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

- (1) 2-Amino methyl benzimidazole and 2-(β-amino ethyl)-benzimidazole were prepared according to the method described by Ceson and Day⁶.
- (2) 2-[β-heteroaryl/aryl-α-amino ethyl]-benzimidazole dihydrochlorides were prepared by the modification of a procedure adopted earlier.⁷

Thus a solution of (0.15 mole) appropriate amino acid and (0.1 mole) aromatic diamine in 5.5N-HCl (100 ml) was heated under reflux for 80 hr until the starting diamine was no longer detectable. The reaction mixture was cooled overnight and the crude dihydrochloride was filtered and recrystallised from dry ethanol. The sample for analysis was dried for 6 hr over dry potassium hydroxide pellets at 110° and 5 mm pressure. The disappearance of peaks in the region 1850-1587 cm⁻¹ due to carbonyl group suggests that cyclization to benzimidazole nucleus has taken place.

- (3) Dialkyl amino acetyl chloride hydrochlorides were prepared by the method described by Sen *et al.*⁸
- (4) Four N₄-aryl/alkyl N₁-chloroacetyl-piperazines have been prepared following the method of Shin Hayao *et al.*⁹

Out of these 4 prepared by us only 2 were reported by authors^{9,10}. The analytical and spectral

TABLE I

2-[β-heteroaryl/aryl-α-amino ethyl]-benzimidazole dihydrochloride

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Composition	(% Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	3-indolyl	230	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ Cl ₂	16.04	15.98
2.	p-hydroxyphenyl	180	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl ₂ O	12.88	12.52
3.	4-(5)-imidazolyl	170	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	23.33	22.86

yield ranges from 60-70%.

TABLE 2

2-[(N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-piperazino carbonyl-methyl)aminoalkyl]-benzimidazole

S. No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Composition	% Nitrogen	
					Calcd.	Found
1	1	phenyl	131	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₅ O	20.05	19.98
2	1	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	225	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₅ ClO	18.27	18.22
3	1	<i>o</i> -tolyl	78	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₅ O	19.28	18.88
4	1	methyl	100	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ O	24.39	23.88
5	2	phenyl	80	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O	19.28	18.58
6	2	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	230	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₅ ClO	17.63	17.24
7	2	<i>o</i> -tolyl	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₅ O	18.56	18.24
8	2	methyl	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ O	23.25	22.98

TABLE 3

2-[(β-dialkylaminomethyl carbonyl amino)-alkyl]-benzimidazole

Sl. no.	X	NR ₁ R ₂	*M.P. °C	Composition	%Nitrogen	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	1	dimethylamino	112	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	24.13	23.98
2.	1	diethylamino	160	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	21.53	20.94
3.	1	piperidino	197	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	20.58	20.42
4.	2	dimethylamino	170	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	22.76	22.24
5.	2	diethylamino	162	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	20.43	20.12
6.	2	piperidino	110	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	19.58	19.14

* The melting points are uncorrected. Yield ranges from 40–50% in Tables 1 and 2.

data in case of known compounds were identical with ours. The analytical and spectral data of unknown compounds are as follows. N₄-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-N₁-chloroacetyl piperazine. M.P. 99°, composition C₁₂H₁₄N₂Cl₂O. Found : N, 10.12%, requires N, 10.25%. I.R. shows an intense band at 1662 cm⁻¹ (amide carbonyl) N₄-(*o*-tolyl)-N₁-chloro acetyl piperazine. M.P. 112°, composition C₁₃H₁₇N₂ClO. Found : N, 11.02%, requires N, 11.11%. Intense band at 1630 cm⁻¹ (amide carbonyl).

(5) 2-[N₄-Aryl/alkyl-N₁-piperazino carbonyl-methyl]-amino alkyl]-benzimidazoles.

To (0.1 mole) N₄-aryl/alkyl-N₁-chloro acetyl-piperazine in absolute alcohol was added 0.1 mole of 2-amino-alkyl benzimidazole and 1 gm freshly ignited potassium carbonate. The resultant mixture was refluxed for 2 hr on a steam bath under anhydrous conditions. After the reaction was over, the solution was filtered and the solvent removed at reduced

pressure. The solid thus left was recrystallised from benzene.

(6) 2-[(β -Dialkyl amino methyl carbonyl amino) alkylbenzimidazole.

To 2-amino alkylbenzimidazole (0.1 mole) in dry chloroform (50 ml), dialkylamino acetyl chloride hydrochloride (0.08 M) in dry chloroform (20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring during 15 min. After refluxing the reaction mixture for 2 hr on a water bath, it was cooled; washed with saturated potassium carbonate solution, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and filtered, chloroform was removed under vacuum and the residual solid was recrystallised from ethanol.

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